

EFFECT OF IRRIGATION AND FERTIGATION LEVELS ON YIELD AND ECONOMICS OF WATERMELON (*Citrullus lanatus* Thunb.)V. D. Tayade¹, A. M. Sonkamble², P. K. Nagre³, V. S. Kale⁴, S. B. Wadatkar⁵, R. D. Walke⁶¹Ph. D. Scholar, Department of Vegetable Science,

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(MS Received: 08.06.2023; MS Revised: 19.07.2023; MS Accepted: 20.07.2023)

MS 3078

(RESEARCH PAPER IN VEGETABLE SCIENCE)

Abstract

The present study entitled "Irrigation and fertigation studies in watermelon" was carried at Instructional farm, Department of Vegetable Science, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, during the year 2018-19 and 2019-20. The experiment was laid out in Strip Plot Design with nine treatment combinations and each treatment replicated thrice. The treatments comprised of three irrigation levels (I) viz., I₁ (100% of irrigation water requirement), I₂ (80% of irrigation water requirement) and I₃ (60% of irrigation water requirement) and three fertigation levels (F) viz., F₁ (125% RDF through fertigation), F₂ (100% RDF through fertigation) and F₃ (75% RDF through fertigation). Observations were recorded in respect of yield and yield contributing characters and economics of the treatments. The yield and yield contributing characters viz., number of pickings, number of fruits per vine, average fruit weight (kg), fruit yield per vine (kg), fruit yield per plot (kg) and fruit yield per hectare (t) was recorded significantly maximum under the irrigation level treatment I₂ (80% irrigation water requirement) and 125% RDF through fertigation (F₁). While the irrigation level treatment (I₃) and 75% RDF through fertigation (F₃) recorded lowest values for all the characters. The treatment combination I₂F₁ (80% irrigation water requirement + 125% RDF through fertigation) showed best performance for all the characters and it was found at par with the treatment I₂F₂. The interaction effect between irrigation levels and fertigation levels i.e., I₂F₁ (80 % of irrigation water requirement + 125% RDF through fertigation) was found superior for obtaining higher net monetary returns and benefit cost ratio.

Keywords: Watermelon, Irrigation levels, Fertigation levels, Yield, Economics**Introduction**

Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* Thunb) belongs to the family Cucurbitaceae and it is the only cultivated species of genus *Citrullus* (Bisognin, 2002). It is a popular dessert fruit, grown in tropical and the Mediterranean regions of the world and believed to have originated in Africa (Simmonds, 1979). In India current status of watermelon area is 115.0 Mha with production 3205.0 MT and productivity 27.9 MT/ha. Maharashtra is the leading state for the watermelon cultivation and current area is 4.46 Mha and production 99.78 MT with 22.37 MT/ha productivity (Anon., 2020-21). It is a commercially important crop in India and the most popular among melons grown in summer. Watermelon comprises 95% water; therefore, water supply to the crop is very critical during growth and development of the plant and fruit. Water shortage causes noticeable gaps in production, with reduction in leaf area and over all yields. Supply of water throughout the growth period is important, but absolutely critical during flowering and fruit development. Water and nutrient management plays an important role in production and productivity.

Efficient use of available irrigation water is essential for increasing agricultural production for the alarming Indian population. Water availability for irrigation is going to be a major constraint for agriculture in near future. Hence, judicious use of the available water resources through more efficient methods of water application like drip irrigation under conditions of protected cultivation becomes necessary to enhance yield and water use efficiency (Dunage *et al.* 2010). Drip fertigation is an important irrigation-cum-nutrient application method in crop production, particularly, in arid and semi-arid regions where there is a high competition for available water resources. Drip irrigation under plastic mulch is an effective way of supplying water efficiently in watermelon cultivation. This may reduce total water requirement besides increasing water use efficiency. To reduce cost of production and environmental pollution, judicious use of water and nutrients is very important.

Fertigation combines two main inputs required for plant growth and development i.e., water and nutrients. The right combination of water and nutrients is the key for high yield and quality of fruit. Fertigation has flexibility, cost effectiveness and the potential for improved seasonal fertilizer application efficiency over traditional fertilizer application methods. Accurate supply of nutrients and water will result in better water use efficiency, avoid stress situations and promote production (Raviv and Blom, 2001). Hence, the present field experiment was set up to determine influence of irrigation and fertigation levels on yield and economics of watermelon.

Material and Methods

The field experiment was conducted at Instructional Farm, Department of Vegetable Science, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola during *rabi* - *summer* season 2018-2019 and 2019-20. The experiment was laid out in strip-plot design (SPD) with two factors (i) three irrigation levels and (ii) three fertigation levels replicated three times. The treatment details in irrigation levels were, I₁:100% of irrigation water requirement (IWR); I₂:80% IWR; I₃:60% IWR and in fertigation levels, F₁:125% recommended dose of fertilizer (RDF) through fertigation; F₂:100% RDF through fertigation; F₃:75% RDF through fertigation. RDF were: 200:100:100 kg NPK ha⁻¹. The nine combinations of irrigation and fertigation levels were also evaluated.

The water-soluble fertilizers such as 19:19:19 and urea and drip irrigation systems were used for irrigation and fertigation purposes. Watermelon (Var. F₁-hybrid) seedlings were raised in portrays for 15 days before being transplanted to the main field at a spacing of 2 x 1m. Fruits were harvested when they made a dull sound when tapped or when the fruits surface on the ground level turned yellow. All other management interventions were carried out in accordance with the university's standard package of practices. A suitable drip set was required for irrigating the crop through drip irrigation. Firstly, for land preparation, harrowing was done once by means of tractor. All the trash of previous weeds was removed from the field. Land smoothing and pulverizing of soil were done by rotavator. The

broad bed was formed at 2 m spacing with approximately height of 30 cm. Accordingly, the layout was prepared and the pipeline for irrigation was installed. The water was conveyed to on-line drip through the pipe lines installed at the experimental site. The irrigation system mainly consists of mainline, sub mainline, on-line lateral, screen filter, manifold, accessories such as control valve, lateral valve, tee, reducer, elbow, coupling, G.T.O, end cap, etc.

Irrigation to watermelon crop was scheduled on every alternate day considering the cumulative pan evaporation of previous two days. In this experiment soluble fertilizers (Urea and 19:19:19 complex) were used. The recommended fertilizer dose of 200:100:100 N, P and K Kg/ha was applied as per the treatments through fertigation. The fertigation was done twice in a week at the morning time. The micronutrients were applied through foliar sprays as per requirement.

Result and Discussion

Yield and Yield attributing parameters

Yield and yield contributing characters viz., number of pickings, number of fruits per vine, average fruit weight (kg), fruit yield per vine (kg), fruit yield per plot (kg) and fruit yield per hectare (t) were significantly influenced by different irrigation and fertigation levels.

Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on number of pickings

The observations were recorded on number of pickings in watermelon as influenced by irrigation and fertigation levels are presented in Table 1.

Effect of irrigation levels on number of pickings

The pooled data regarding number of pickings during both the year differed significantly. Treatment I₂ (80% of irrigation water requirement), produced maximum number of pickings (2.21) which was followed by the treatment I₁ (1.97), whereas minimum number of pickings was recorded by treatment I₃ (1.88) where 60% of irrigation water requirement.

Effect of fertigation levels on number of pickings

The pooled data regarding number of pickings of both the years differed significantly. The treatment F₁ (125% RDF through fertigation) produced maximum number of pickings (2.16) which was at par treatment F₂ (2.00), whereas minimum number of pickings were recorded by the treatment F₃ (1.90) which received 75% RDF through fertigation.

Interaction effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on number of pickings

The data presented in Table 1 indicated that, the interaction of irrigation and fertigation levels on number of pickings was found to be non-significant during both the years of experimentation (2018-19 and 2019-20) and pooled mean.

Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on number of fruits per vine

The observations were recorded on number of fruits per vine in watermelon as influenced by irrigation and fertigation levels are presented in Table 2.

Effect of irrigation levels on number of fruits per vine

The pooled data regarding number of fruits per vine during both the year differed significantly. Treatment I₂ (80% of irrigation water requirement), produced maximum number of fruits per vine (2.13) which was derived by with the treatment I₁ (1.98), whereas minimum number of fruits per vine was recorded by treatment I₃ (1.94) where 60% of irrigation water requirement.

Effect of fertigation levels on number of fruits per vine

The pooled data regarding number of fruits per vine of both the years differed significantly. The treatment F₁ (125% RDF through fertigation) produced maximum number of fruits per vine (2.16) followed by treatment F₂ (1.99), whereas minimum number of fruits per vine was recorded by the treatment F₃ (1.91) which received 75% RDF through fertigation.

Interaction effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on number of fruits per vine

The data presented in Table 2 indicated that, the interaction of irrigation and fertigation levels on number of fruits per vine was

found to be non-significant during both the years of experimentation (2018-19 and 2019-20) and pooled mean.

Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on average fruit weight (kg)

The observations were recorded on average fruit weight (kg) in watermelon as influenced by irrigation and fertigation levels are presented in Table 3.

Effect of irrigation levels on average fruit weight (kg)

The pooled data regarding average fruit weight during both the year differed significantly. Treatment I₂ (80% of irrigation water requirement) produced maximum average fruit weight (3.40kg), which was followed by the treatment I₁ (2.88kg), whereas minimum average fruit weight was recorded by treatment I₃ (2.78kg) where 60% of irrigation water requirement was provided.

Effect of fertigation levels on average fruit weight (kg)

The pooled data regarding average fruit weight (kg) of both the years differed significantly. The treatment F₁ (125% RDF through fertigation) produced maximum average fruit weight (3.26kg) followed by treatment F₂ (3.09kg), whereas minimum average fruit weight was recorded by the treatment F₃ (2.71kg) which received 75% RDF through fertigation.

Interaction effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on average fruit weight (kg)

The pooled data regarding average fruit weight (kg) differed significantly during both the years under study. The treatment combination of I₂F₁ (80% irrigation water requirement along with 125% RDF through fertigation) produced maximum average fruit weight (3.81kg) which was followed by I₂F₂ (3.65kg). Whereas, minimum average fruit weight was recorded by the treatment I₃F₃ (2.68kg) which was 60% irrigation water requirement along with 75% RDF through fertigation.

Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on fruit yield per vine (kg)

The observations were recorded on fruit yield per vine (kg) in watermelon as influenced by irrigation and fertigation levels are presented in Table 4.

Effect of irrigation levels on fruit yield per vine (kg)

The pooled data regarding fruit yield per vine (kg) during both the year differed significantly. Treatment I₂ (80% of irrigation water requirement), produced maximum fruit yield per vine (7.31kg) was followed by the treatment I₁ (5.70kg), whereas minimum fruit yield per vine was recorded by treatment I₁ (5.42kg) where 60% of irrigation water requirement.

Effect of fertigation levels on fruit yield per vine (kg)

The pooled data regarding fruit yield per vine (kg) in both the years differed significantly. The treatment F₁ (125% RDF through fertigation) produced maximum fruit yield per vine (7.07kg) followed by treatment F₂ (6.19kg), whereas minimum fruit yield per vine was recorded by the treatment F₃ (5.18kg) which received 75% RDF through fertigation.

Interaction effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on fruit yield per vine (kg)

The pooled data regarding fruit yield per vine (kg) differed significantly during both the years under study. The treatment combination of I₂F₁ (80% irrigation water requirement along with 125% RDF through fertigation) produced maximum fruit yield per vine (8.75kg) which was followed by treatment combination I₂F₂ (7.77kg) Whereas, minimum fruit yield per vine was recorded by the treatment I₃F₃ (5.01) which was 60% irrigation water requirement along with 75% RDF through fertigation.

Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on fruit yield per plot (kg)

The observations were recorded on fruit yield per plot (kg) in watermelon as influenced by irrigation and fertigation levels are presented in Table 5.

Effect of irrigation levels on fruit yield per plot (kg)

The pooled data regarding fruit yield per plot (kg) during both the year differed significantly. Treatment I₂ (80% of irrigation water requirement), produced maximum fruit yield per plot (73.14kg) which was followed by the treatment I₁ (57.19kg), whereas minimum fruit yield per plot was recorded by treatment I₃ (54.03kg) where 60% of irrigation water requirement was applied.

Effect of fertigation levels on fruit yield per plot (kg)

The pooled data regarding fruit yield per plot (kg) of both the years differed significantly. The treatment F₁ (125% RDF through fertigation) produced maximum fruit yield per plot (70.65kg) followed by treatment F₂ (61.83kg), whereas minimum fruit yield per plot was recorded by the treatment F₃ (51.87kg) which received 75% RDF through fertigation.

Interaction effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on fruit yield per plot (kg)

The pooled data regarding fruit yield per plot (kg) differed significantly during both the years under study. The treatment combination of I₂F₁ (80% irrigation water requirement + 125% RDF through fertigation) produced maximum fruit yield per plot (87.51kg) which was at par with treatment I₂F₂ (77.85kg). Whereas, minimum fruit yield per plot was recorded by the treatment I₃F₃ (50.02kg) which was 60% irrigation water requirement along with 75% RDF through fertigation.

Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on fruit yield per hectare (t)

The observations were recorded on fruit yield per hectare (t) in watermelon as influenced by irrigation and fertigation levels are presented in Table 6.

Effect of irrigation levels on fruit yield per hectare (t)

The pooled data regarding fruit yield per hectare (t) during both the year differed significantly. Treatment I₂ (80% of irrigation water requirement), produced maximum fruit yield per hectare (36.57t) which was followed by the treatment I₁ (28.59t), whereas minimum fruit yield per hectare was recorded by treatment I₃ (27.01t) where 60% of irrigation water requirement. The results are in conformity with Erdem *et al.* (2001) in watermelon, Roupheal *et al.* (2008) in watermelon and Nisha *et al.* (2020) in watermelon.

Effect of fertigation levels on fruit yield per hectare (t)

The pooled data regarding fruit yield per hectare (t) of both the years differed significantly. The treatment F₁ (125% RDF through fertigation) produced maximum fruit yield per hectare (35.32t) followed by treatment F₂ (30.92t), whereas minimum fruit yield per hectare was recorded by the treatment F₃ (25.94t) which received 75% RDF through fertigation.

At higher fertigation level, crop meets its nutritional requirement at respective growth stages which leads to luxuriance growth and thereby enhancement of fruit yield. Drip fertigation with water soluble fertilizers improved the root system by inducing the effect on the root architecture especially in the production of higher fibrous root system. Greater efficiency of nutrients has been achieved by matching the daily supplies of nutrient to the demand according to plant development stage. The frequent application of nutrients as per requirement of crop growth stages enhances the physiological activities for luxurious and healthy crop growth for maximum production of biomass resulted in higher translocation of photosynthesis towards yield attributes for their development. The increase in fruit production with more frequent fertigation is attributable to the enhanced availability and uptake of nutrients by plants over soil application of fertilizers which results in better growth and increased fruit production with better availability of nutrient throughout the growth stages leading to better uptake of nutrients and its production of watermelon. Similar results were also reported by Sahin *et al.* (2015) in cucumber, Kumawat (2015) in cucumber and Nisha *et al.* (2020) in watermelon.

Interaction effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on fruit yield per hectare (t)

The pooled data regarding fruit yield per hectare (t) differed significantly during both the years under study. The treatment combination of I₂F₁ (80% irrigation water requirement along with 125% RDF through fertigation) produced maximum fruit yield per hectare (43.75t) which was followed by I₂F₂ (38.93t). Whereas, minimum fruit yield per hectare was recorded by the treatment I₃F₃ (25.01t) which was 60% irrigation water requirement along with 75% RDF through fertigation.

Increase in crop yield due to higher NPK and optimum level of water irrigation at shorter intervals was possible due to good synchronization between crop demand and nutrient availability which ultimately leads to higher nutrient use efficiency. The results are in line of the findings by Cabello *et al.* (2009) in muskmelon, Gupta *et al.* (2014) in cucumber, Nigaraju and Joseph (2014) in pickling melon, Abraham *et al.* (2017) in bitter gourd and Nisha *et al.* (2020) in watermelon.

Economics

The data regarding economics i.e., for benefit-cost (B:C) ratio, was significantly differed by irrigation and fertigation levels.

Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on benefit: cost (B:C) ratio of watermelon

The benefit: cost ratio of watermelon production as influenced by irrigation and fertigation levels significantly differed and is presented in Table 7.

Interaction effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on B:C ratio

The result data of benefit cost ratio as influenced by interaction effect due to irrigation and fertigation levels, which is presented in Table 7.

The pooled data indicated that, significantly highest benefit cost ratio (3.06) was obtained by the treatment I₂F₁ (80% irrigation water requirement along with 125% RDF through fertigation) followed by I₂F₂ (2.44) respectively. The least benefit cost ratio (1.73) was obtained from the treatment combination I₃F₂ (60% irrigation water requirement along with 100% RDF through fertigation).

Any technology before recommendation has to be tested on the basis of economic viability from the growers point for adoption. Irrigation and Fertigation in vegetable crops require higher capital investment particularly when water soluble fertilizers are used along with fertigation system. Hence, the economic viability of drip fertigation system was calculated considering the longer life span of the drip system, increased productivity and net extra income over conventional fertilization. However, due to higher uptake of nutrients and nutrient use efficiency the water-soluble fertilizers registered higher gross income through significantly higher yields.

Thus, the extra expenditure towards water soluble fertilizers was well compensated through higher additional income high net return in watermelon could be assured by increasing the productivity by adopting proven management practices. In the present study, application of 80% irrigation water and 125% RDF through fertigation secured the highest net income. This resulted in the production of higher yield per hectare with higher cost benefit ratio. The similar results are in agreement with the findings by Hakim and Chand (2014) in cucumber, Kumawat (2015) in cucumber and Nisha *et al.* (2020) in watermelon.

Conclusion

On the basis of the findings reported in present investigation the effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on yield and economics of watermelon was found to be promising. Amongst the different irrigation levels, the treatment 80% irrigation water requirement was found to be the best treatment in respect to yield and yield attributing parameters *viz.*, number of pickings, number of fruits per vine, average fruit weight (kg), fruit yield per vine (kg), fruit yield per plot (kg) and fruit yield per hectare (t). While in respect of fertigation levels 125% RDF through fertigation was found to significantly maximum in all the yield and yield attributing parameters. Interaction effect of irrigation levels and fertigation levels 80% irrigation water requirement along with 125% RDF through fertigation was found

superior for obtaining maximum yield of watermelon with higher net monetary returns and benefit cost ratio.

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Table 1. Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on number of pickings

Number of pickings												
Treatment	2018-19				2019-20				Pooled			
	Fertigation levels (F)				Fertigation levels (F)				Fertigation levels (F)			
Irrigation levels (I)	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean
I ₁	2.13	1.93	1.80	1.96	2.20	1.87	1.87	1.98	2.17	1.90	1.83	1.97
I ₂	2.27	2.20	2.13	2.20	2.33	2.27	2.07	2.22	2.30	2.23	2.10	2.21
I ₃	1.87	1.80	1.80	1.82	2.13	1.93	1.73	1.93	2.00	1.87	1.77	1.88
Mean	2.09	1.98	1.91		2.22	2.02	1.89		2.16	2.00	1.90	
	I	F	IXF		I	F	IXF		I	F	IXF	
F' test	Sig	Sig	NS		Sig	Sig	NS		Sig	Sig	NS	
SE(m)±	0.07	0.03	0.10		0.03	0.05	0.11		0.04	0.03	0.07	
CD at 5%	0.27	0.13	-		0.12	0.20	-		0.15	0.13	-	

Table 2. Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on number of fruits per vine

Number of fruits per vine												
Treatment	2018-19				2019-20				Pooled			
	Fertigation levels (F)				Fertigation levels (F)				Fertigation levels (F)			
Irrigation levels (I)	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean
I ₁	2.07	1.93	1.80	1.93	2.13	1.93	2.00	2.02	2.10	1.93	1.90	1.98
I ₂	2.27	2.07	2.07	2.13	2.33	2.20	1.87	2.13	2.30	2.13	1.97	2.13
I ₃	2.20	2.00	1.87	2.02	1.93	1.80	1.87	1.87	2.07	1.90	1.87	1.94
Mean	2.18	2.00	1.91		2.13	1.98	1.91		2.16	1.99	1.91	
	I	F	IXF		I	F	IXF		I	F	IXF	
F' test	Sig	Sig	NS		Sig	Sig	NS		Sig	Sig	NS	
SE(m)±	0.03	0.05	0.12		0.03	0.04	0.09		0.02	0.03	0.10	
CD at 5%	0.13	0.18	-		0.13	0.15	-		0.09	0.13	-	

Table 3. Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on average fruit weight (kg)

Average fruit weight (kg)												
Treatment	2018-19				2019-20				Pooled			
	Fertigation levels (F)				Fertigation levels (F)				Fertigation levels (F)			
Irrigation levels (I)	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean
I ₁	2.71	2.67	2.56	2.65	3.42	3.07	2.85	3.11	3.07	2.87	2.71	2.88
I ₂	3.68	3.56	2.68	3.31	3.93	3.73	2.82	3.49	3.81	3.65	2.75	3.40
I ₃	2.77	2.63	2.55	2.65	3.04	2.87	2.81	2.91	2.91	2.75	2.68	2.78
Mean	3.06	2.96	2.60		3.46	3.22	2.82		3.26	3.09	2.71	

	I	F	IXF		I	F	IXF		I	F	IXF	
F' test	Sig	Sig	Sig		Sig	Sig	Sig		Sig	Sig	Sig	
SE(m)±	0.04	0.04	0.08		0.04	0.04	0.05		0.01	0.02	0.04	
CD at 5%	0.15	0.14	0.25		0.14	0.15	0.16		0.06	0.08	0.12	

Table 4. Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on fruit yield per vine (kg)

Fruit yield per vine												
	2018-19				2019-20				Pooled			
Treatment	Fertigation levels (F)				Fertigation levels (F)				Fertigation levels (F)			
Irrigation levels (I)	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean
I₁	5.60	5.13	4.61	5.11	7.31	5.97	5.69	6.32	6.43	5.55	5.13	5.70
I₂	8.33	7.36	5.56	7.09	9.17	8.21	5.25	7.54	8.75	7.77	5.41	7.31
I₃	6.10	5.27	4.75	5.37	5.88	5.16	5.25	5.43	6.03	5.24	5.01	5.42
Mean	6.68	5.92	4.97		7.45	6.44	5.40		7.07	6.19	5.18	
	I	F	IXF		I	F	IXF		I	F	IXF	
F' test	Sig	Sig	Sig		Sig	Sig	Sig		Sig	Sig	Sig	
SE(m)±	0.15	0.09	0.29		0.14	0.19	0.34		0.08	0.11	0.28	
CD at 5%	0.58	0.35	0.88		0.55	0.74	1.10		0.30	0.42	0.92	

Table 5. Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on fruit yield per plot (kg)

Fruit yield per plot (kg)												
	2018-19				2019-20				Pooled			
Treatment	Fertigation levels (F)				Fertigation levels (F)				Fertigation levels (F)			
Irrigation levels (I)	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean
I₁	55.97	51.33	46.14	51.15	73.08	59.66	56.93	63.22	64.52	55.49	51.54	57.19
I₂	83.34	73.63	55.59	70.85	91.68	82.07	52.55	75.43	87.51	77.85	54.07	73.14
I₃	61.00	52.70	47.52	53.74	58.83	51.59	52.51	54.31	59.91	52.15	50.02	54.03
Mean	66.77	59.22	49.75		74.53	64.44	54.00		70.65	61.83	51.87	
	I	F	IXF		I	F	IXF		I	F	IXF	
F' test	Sig	Sig	Sig		Sig	Sig	Sig		Sig	Sig	Sig	
SE(m)±	1.48	0.88	2.90		1.39	1.89	3.37		0.80	1.04	2.80	
CD at 5%	5.82	3.46	8.72		5.45	7.42	10.99		3.13	4.08	9.13	

Table 6. Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on fruit yield per hectare (t)

Fruit yield per hectare (t)												
Treatment	2018-19				2019-20				Pooled			
	Fertigation levels (F)				Fertigation levels (F)				Fertigation levels (F)			
Irrigation levels (I)	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean
I ₁	27.98	25.66	23.07	25.57	36.54	29.83	28.47	31.61	32.26	27.75	25.77	28.59
I ₂	41.67	36.81	27.79	35.43	45.84	41.04	26.27	37.72	43.75	38.93	27.03	36.57
I ₃	30.50	26.35	23.76	26.87	29.41	25.80	26.26	27.16	29.96	26.07	25.01	27.01
Mean	33.38	29.61	24.87		37.26	32.22	27.00		35.32	30.92	25.94	
	I	F	IXF		I	F	IXF		I	F	IXF	
F' test	Sig	Sig	Sig		Sig	Sig	Sig		Sig	Sig	Sig	
SE(m)±	0.74	0.44	1.45		0.69	0.94	1.69		0.40	0.52	1.40	
CD at 5%	2.91	1.73	4.36		2.73	3.71	5.50		1.57	2.04	4.56	

Table 7. Effect of irrigation and fertigation levels on economics of watermelon (B:C ratio)

Treatments	2018-19				2019-20				Pooled			
	Cost of cultivation (Rs ha-1)	Gross income (Rs ha-1)	Net income (Rs ha-1)	B:C Ratio	Cost of cultivation (Rs ha-1)	Gross income (Rs ha-1)	Net income (Rs ha-1)	B:C Ratio	Cost of cultivation (Rs ha-1)	Gross income (Rs ha-1)	Net income (Rs ha-1)	B:C Ratio
I ₁ F ₁	247103	405710	158607	1.64	158293	475020	316727	3.00	202698	440365	237667	2.32
I ₁ F ₂	265327	372070	106743	1.40	164853	387790	222937	2.35	215090	379930	164840	1.88
I ₁ F ₃	246785	334515	87730	1.36	155846	370110	214264	2.37	201316	352313	150997	1.87
I ₂ F ₁	242631	604215	361584	2.49	164412	595920	431508	3.62	203521	600068	396546	3.06
I ₂ F ₂	276999	533745	256746	1.93	180340	533520	353180	2.96	228669	533633	304963	2.44
I ₂ F ₃	252458	402955	150497	1.60	157526	341510	183984	2.17	204992	372233	167240	1.88
I ₃ F ₁	246689	442250	195561	1.79	153713	382330	228617	2.49	200201	412290	212089	2.14
I ₃ F ₂	262381	382075	119694	1.46	168001	335400	167399	2.00	215191	358738	143546	1.73
I ₃ F ₃	250525	344520	93995	1.38	153607	341380	187773	2.22	202066	342950	140884	1.80